

SUSTAINABILITY OF WASTE RECYCLING BUSINESS ADMIST COVID – 19 PANDEMIC

Aljhon M. Bulalague, Aldrin A. Drew

College of Business Administration and Accountancy, AMA University, Quezon City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13929023>

ABSTRACT

Waste recycling business or junkshops are common in the Philippines. The operation focuses on recycling materials such as, used plastic bottles, cans, steels, papers and other materials that can be recycled. Many would not enter the industry due to its "scrappy" nature since it deals with unclean and reject materials. Filipinos buy junks by the kilogram, with paper as the cheapest (price ranging from 50 cents to Php15 per kg) and batteries and certain types of metal as most expensive. The junkshops sell almost all types of plastics, whole or broken glasses, metals, papers, and vehicle batteries. In March 2020, the world has faced the threat of COVID-19 pandemic. Many countries struggled fighting the virus and many have lost their jobs and some lost their lives. As the world faced the viruses many businessmen especially in Philippines had a hard time to sustain their business. Business owners were forced to close or stop the operation due to limited customers and limited operation they can perform. Some junkshops owners cannot operate like picking-up the scrap materials from their customers and delivering scrap in larger junkshop since city boundaries required passers to have documents such as quarantine pass or vaccination card. The operation becomes limited due to national and local restrictions. Based on the context above, the researcher came up with this study, SUSTAINABILITY OF WASTE RECYCLING BUSINESS AMIDST COVID-19 PANDEMIC.

Keywords: *Waste Recycle, Sustainability, Junkshops, Covid-19 Pandemic, Recycling Business*

INTRODUCTION

Waste recycling business or junkshops are common in the Philippines, its operation focuses on recycling materials such as, used plastic bottles, cans, steels, papers and other materials that can be recycled (Coracero et al., 2021). Many would not enter industry due to its “scrappy” nature since, it deals with unclean and reject materials that are usually smelly. Junkshops are profitable business since they deal with the waste coming from the products used by the humans. Those waste products can be recycled to generate another product such as used paper can be turned into notebook, window frame can turn into steel bar to use in construction (Adeniran & Shakantu, 2022).

The junkshops buy almost all types of plastics, whole or broken glasses, metals, papers, and vehicle batteries (Romallosa et al., 2024). They buy junks by the kilogram, with paper as the cheapest (price ranging from 50 cents to Php15 per kg.) and with batteries and certain types of metal as most expensive (price ranging from 50 to 70 Php per kg).

In March 2020, the world has faced the threat of Covid-19 pandemic. Many countries struggled fighting the virus and many has lost their jobs and some lost their lives (Jocson, 2023.). The struggle is real during the Covid-19 pandemic, as the world faced the virus many businesses especially in Philippines had a hard time to sustain its business and one of them is the waste recycling industry or junkshops (Balaria et al., 2021). The operation become limited due to national and local restrictions. Some junkshop owners cannot operate like picking-up the scrap materials from their customers and delivering scrap in larger junkshop since city boundaries required passers to have documents such as quarantine pass or vaccination card. The researcher wants to determine how junkshop owners sustain their business even amidst the Covid-19 pandemic and also, to know what is the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic to waste recycling business or junkshop (Ebner & Iacovidou, 2021). The study titled, Sustainability of waste recycling business amidst Covid-19 pandemic investigated how the junkshop owners sustained their businesses amidst the Covid-19 pandemic. This study also provides insights to the readers, researchers and other people as it may serve as a guide on how the owners sustain their business amidst the Covid-19 pandemic.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the sustainability of waste recycling business amidst the Covid-19 pandemic.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. How may the business be described as to:
 - 1.1 initial capital;
 - 1.2 years in operation; and
 - 1.3 number of workers?
2. How does the Covid-19 pandemic affect the waste recycling business?
3. What practices were undertaken by the respondents to sustain their waste recycling business during the Covid-19 pandemic in terms of:

- 3.1 people;
- 3.2 profit; and
- 3.3 planet?

4. What challenges are encountered by the respondent and how were these minimized?

5. How may the findings be utilized to craft measures to minimize the impact of Covid-19 pandemic in waste recycling business?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The objective of descriptive research is to accurately and methodically describe a group of people, event, or phenomenon. A descriptive research plan can look at one or more variables using a wide range of research techniques. In contrast to experimental research, here the variables are only seen and measured; no controls or manipulations are made McCombes (2020). Descriptive study was used by the researcher since it is thought to provide answers regarding how junkshop owners maintain their businesses in the face of the COVID-19 epidemic.

Scope and Delimitation

The study aimed to determine the sustainability of waste recycling business during the pandemic. The research study focused on junkshop owners in Quezon City. This is limited to fifty (50) junkshop owners who still operated during the lockdown at Quezon City during the Calendar Year 2021.

Respondents

The respondents of this study are fifty (50) junkshop owners in Quezon City who is still operated during lockdown. The researcher was confident that this number is enough to gather the needed information for this study.

Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling technique is a non-probability sampling technique in which information is gathered from a readily available and accessible population (Elfil & Negida, 2017).. The sample is made up of people who are most conveniently available to the researcher rather than those who are most representative of the population as a whole (Simkus 2022). The researcher used convenience sampling technique to gathered the data from the respondents. The researcher was confident that the data gathered from the respondent are credible.

Instruments

The instrument used by the researcher is a questionnaire which he believed that it is an accurate way to gather information from the respondents.

Questionnaire is the primary source of data. This contains questions stated in Chapter 1. The participants were asked to check the items that correspond to the answers to the questions. The questionnaire was composed of four (4) parts. Part 1 is about the profile of the junkshops (initial capital, years of operation, and number of workers) Part 2 is about the effects of Covid-19 pandemic to waste recycling business Part 3 consists of the practices undertaken by the respondent to sustain the business during COVID-19 Pandemic Part 4 are the challenges encountered by the respondents and were these addressed.

Construction and Validation of the Instrument

The researcher read books, magazine, article, thesis, dissertation related to the topic to formulate the concept of the study. The researcher pre-tested the instrument used to three (3) junkshop owners who were not part of the respondent. The purpose of this is to find out if the questionnaire is vague or has a confusing item.

Administration and Retrieval of the Instrument

The researcher personally administered the distribution of the questionnaires to the junkshop owners. They were asked them to accomplish the form on the day it was given to them. This was done to ensure one hundred percent (100%) retrieval of the questionnaire.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools were used by the researchers on this study.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. is a data presentation that indicates the proportion of observations for each data point or set of data points. It is a very helpful way to represent other data, such as the relative frequency of survey replies. $P = \frac{f}{(n)} \times 100$

Where:

P = percentage

f = frequency

n = number of respondents

Weighted mean. It was used to measure the holistic view of the respondents' responses. Each statement has four responses classified under the level of frequency with weights 1, 2, 3, and 4.

The corresponding point assigned by estimating each weighted average with the

following equivalent verbal description.

$$M = \frac{\sum wf}{n}$$

Where:

WM= weighted mean

w= weight assigned

F= frequencies for each option

$\sum wf$ = sum of all weighted scores obtained by a sample

N= number of respondents in a sample

Numerical Limits	Scale	Verbal Interpretation
3.26- 4.00	4	Strongly Agree (SA)
2.51 – 3.25	3	Agree (A)
1.76 – 2.50	2	Disagree (D)
1.00-1.75	1	Strongly Disagree (SD)

Ranking. was used to find the positional level of importance of certain items involved in the study.

RESULTS

1. Profile of the respondents

Table 1 Respondents as to Initial Capital

Capital	f	%	Rank
₱ 10,000-₱50,000	3	6	4
₱50,001-₱100,000	14	6	3
₱ 100,001-₱150,000	17	34	1
₱150,001-₱200,000	15	30	2
₱200,001 and above	1	2	5
Total	50	100	

Table 2 Respondents as to Years in Operation

Years in Operation	f	%	Rank
1-5 Years	22	44	1
6-10 Years	11	22	2
11-15 Years	9	18	3
16-20 Years	8	16	4
Total	50	100	

Table 3 Respondents as to Number of Workers

Number of Workers	f	%	Rank
1-3 Workers	23	46	1
4-6 Workers	17	34	2
7-9 Workers	10	20	3
Total	50	100	

2. Effects of Covid-19 pandemic to waste recycling businesses

Table 4 Effects of Covid-19 Pandemic to Waste Recycling Business

Indicators	f	%	Rank
Reduction in business profit	49	18	1
Lay-off of workers	35	13	5
Temporarily shutting down business operations	31	11	6

Liquidation of assets (i.e., selling of business properties)	28	10	7
Downsizing business operation	40	14	4
Limited operation due to lockdown and restriction	47	17	2.5
Scrap materials price went down	47	17	2.5

3. Practices undertaken by the respondents to sustain the business during COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 5 In Terms of People

Indicators	WX	I	Rank
Contacting customers regarding their scrap materials.	2.74	A	4
Attracting new customers thru online and banners.	2.72	A	5
Following the health protocol for employees' safety.	3.00	A	1
Contacting large junk shops to set schedule for delivery.	2.96	A	3
Setting a skeletal scheduling to employees to minimize the expense.	2.98	A	2
Overall Weighten Mean	2.88	A	

Table 6 In Terms of Profit

Indicators	WX	I	Rank
Acquiring additional capital to financial institution to sustain the business.	2.70	A	5
Lowering the buying price of the scraps. (For buyer of scrap)	3.02	A	2
Buying scraps that only produce more profit.	3.08	A	1
Minimizing the operational cost. (i.e., pick-up scheduling)	3.00	A	3
Buying at higher price to match to competitor	2.96	A	4
Overall Weighten Mean	2.95	A	

Table 7 In Terms of Planet

Indicators	WX	I	Rank
Buying scraps that produce less unsaleable waste.	2.40	A	3
Separating face mask, face shield, and other medical supplies to avoid the spread of Covid-19.	2.08	A	5
Disposing only unsaleable scraps when garbage truck is available.	2.64	A	2
Accepting scraps that not coming from medical facilities to avoid the spread of Covid-19.	2.38	A	4
Following the safety protocols such as wearing face mask and social distancing to avoid the spread of Covid-19.	3.30	SA	1
Overall Weighten Mean	2.56	A	

Challenges encountered amidst the Covid-19 pandemic by the respondents

Table 8 Challenges Encountered by the Respondents

Indicators	*f	(%)	Rank
The supply of scrap materials becomes limited.	50	100	1
Some Large Junk Shops had been closed temporarily.	36	72	4.5
Maintenance of vehicle used increases.	31	62	7.5
Lack of income during lockdown.	41	82	3.5
The financial support of the National and Local Government are	31	62	7.5
The price of scrap materials decreases.	41	82	3.5
Some scrap materials labelled as "stop buying".	39	78	4.5
City boundaries checkpoint restriction limits the operation.	46	92	2
Day to day operation expenses increase.	35	70	7.5
Difficulty on disposing the scrap materials.	38	76	4.5

5. Solutions to minimize the impact of Covid-19 pandemic

Table 9 Solutions to Minimize the Impact of Covid-19 Pandemic

Indicators	f	(%)	Rank
Stock scraps and wait for demand to pick up.	48	96	1
Sell other scraps to other junk shops.	35	70	7.5
Limit the use of vehicles to lessen the maintenance	34	68	7.5
Sell other properties to sustain the business.	32	64	7.5
Borrow additional capital to Financial Institution and friends	28	56	10
Reduce the buying price of the scrap.	36	72	4.5
Reject scrap labeled as "stop buying"	38	76	4.5
Prepare necessary documents such as quarantine.	42	84	3
Prepare a budget plan for expenses.	38	76	4.5
Prepare a schedule plan for delivery of scraps.	45	90	2

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the frequency and the percentage distribution of the respondents as to initial capital. As indicated in Table 1, rank 1 is ₱ 100,001-₱ 150,000 with 34 percent. Rank 2 is ₱ 150,001-₱ 200,000 with 30 percent and rank 3 is ₱ 50,001-₱ 100,000. It shows the initial capital of owners to start Junkshop business. The most starting capital is ₱ 100,001-₱ 150,000, It means that the amount is enough to start and maintain the business.

Table 2 presents the frequency and the percentage distribution of the respondents as to years in operation. As indicated in table 2, rank 1 is 1-5 Years with 44 percent. Rank 2 is 6-10 Years with 22 percent, and rank 3 is 11-15 Years with 18 percent. It only shows that most of the respondents are operating for 1-5 years which means they are new to the industry and do not have enough knowledge compared to other junkshop owners who have been operating for decades.

Table 3 presents the frequency and the percentage distribution of the respondents as to number of workers. As indicated in table 3, rank 1 is 1-3 workers with 46 percent. Rank 2 is 4-6 workers with 34 percent, and rank 3 is 7-9 workers with 20 percent. It shows that the 46 percent of the respondents has 1-3 workers which is enough number of employees to operate the business for stacking, loading, and delivering the scrap

materials to another large junkshop.

Table 4 presents the frequency and the percentage distribution on the effects encountered by the respondent. The above table indicates the rank on the effects of Covid-19 pandemic. The reduction in business profit is rank 1 with 18 percent. Tied in Rank 2 are to limited operation due to lockdown and restriction and scrap materials selling price went down with 17 percent. Rank 4 is the downsizing business operation with 14 percent. It only shows that the most of the owners are facing difficulty in generating income since some of the large establishments are closed and the supply of the scrap materials becomes limited due to lockdowns and restrictions. It means that the Covid-19 pandemic becomes a struggle to junkshop owners.

Table 5 Table 5 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on practices undertaken by the respondent to sustain the business during Covid-19 pandemic. As shown on the table, rank 1 which is following the health protocol for employees' safety has a WX pf 3.00 or Agree. Rank 2 pertains to setting a skeletal scheduling to employees to minimize the expense with a WX of 2.98 or Agree, and contacting large junk shops to set schedule for delivery with a WX of 2.96 or Agree. It only shows that the junkshop owners put the safety first of their employees by following the safety protocols such as wearing face mask, social distancing, and sanitizing after a physical contact with customers. The table also denotes that junkshop owners used skeletal system of work scheme to minimize the expenses. Since some of the workers are not stay-in it lessens the expenses especially when it comes to the usage of water and electricity. The table shows that the junkshop owners used to contact the large junkshop to sell their scraps to maximize the time spent in delivering the scrap and also to have a fast transaction to lessen the exposure of the employees to other people.

Table 6 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on practices undertaken by the respondent to sustain the business during covid-19 pandemic. As shown on above table, rank 1 buying scraps that only produce more profit with WX of 3.08 or Agree. Rank 2 with WX of 3.02 or Agree is lowering the buying price of the scraps and Rank 3 is minimizing the operational cost with a WX of 3.00 or Agree. It only signifies that most of the junkshop owners buy scrap that produce more profit to maintain the business such as Bakal (assorted and solid), plastic, tin cans, and copper (Tanso) which are easy to dispose of. On the other hand, lowering the buying price of the scrap helps the business to maintain even in the amidst of pandemic due to higher profit since they can gain more profit. The above table shows that most of the junk shop owners minimize the operational cost of the business such as gas for vehicle, acetylene gas for cutting bulky iron scraps, etc. Thus, the owner can focus more on other expense like salary of the employees and expenses.

Table 7 presents the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation on practices undertaken by the respondent to sustain the business during Covid-19 pandemic. The above table shows, rank 1 that is following the safety protocols such as wearing face mask and social distancing to avoid the spread of Covid-19 with a WX of 3.30 or Agree. Rank 2 is disposing only unsaleable scraps when garbage truck is available with a WX

of 2.64 or Agree, and Rank 3 is buying scraps that produce less unsaleable waste with a WX of 2.40 or Agree. It only shows that the junkshop owners are following the healthy protocols mandated by the local and national government not just to maintain the safety of their employees, but also their customers and the community where the business is located. The table also shows that they disposed the unsaleable materials like T. V's picture tube, Styrofoam from refrigerator, plastic bags, and other scrap that has no value. Furthermore, junkshop owners buy scrap that produce less reject scraps to lessen the space occupied.

Table 8 indicates that rank 1 on the effects encountered is the supply of scrap materials becomes limited with 100 percent. Rank 2 pertains to city boundaries checkpoint restriction limits the operation with 92 percent are rank 3 is lack of income during lockdown and the price of scrap materials decrease with 82 percent. It only shows that the junkshop owners have experienced limited supply of scraps since the covid-19 pandemic limits the outside activities of people and some of the large recycling centers are closed temporarily. In connection with this, city boundaries and checkpoints are also the reason of limited supply of scraps because they cannot get through to deliver their scraps. The table also indicates that they experienced lack of income during the lockdown is because limited number of customers visit the shop due to spread of the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, stated on the table is the price of scrap materials went down during the pandemic. This is because the demand for scrap materials also went down like used papers since the school and office activities become limited.

Table 9 indicates that rank 1 on the solution undertaken by the respondents is the stock scraps and wait for demand to pick up with 96 percent. Rank 2 is preparing a schedule plan for delivery of scraps with 90 percent and rank 3 prepare necessary documents such as quarantine pass with 84 percent. It only showed that the most of the junkshop owners used to stock their scrap and wait for the demand to pick up. This means that owners are maximizing the capital they used to purchase those scraps and hoping that may double the value when the demand of the scraps increases. It also shows that they set a schedule to deliver the scraps. This is because some of the large junkshops only accept those customers that have an appointment to lessen the time spent in the facility and record persons who are coming to the facility. Lastly, it connotes that owner are preparing the necessary document such as quarantine pass for them to deliver the scrap in different city with no hassle and to have easy access.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of the findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Most of the respondents has an initial capital of ₱100,001 - ₱150,000 operating at least 1-5 years and has 1-3 workers.
2. There is an obvious impact of Covid-19 pandemic to junkshop owners with the reduction of profit, operations become limited due to lockdown and restriction and the prices crap materials went down.
3. Junkshop owners had a safety protocol to maintain the safety of their staff. Skeletal

schedule was also implemented by the owners to lessen the daily cost. Respondents buy scraps that produce more profit in able to maintain the business during the Covid-19 pandemic. Junkshop helps to lessen the garbage thrown in the landfill and also, it lessens the air pollutants and avoid clogging the water ways.

4. Most of the respondents have difficulties passing on city boundary checkpoints and respondents have experienced on low income and low supply of scrap materials.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of the findings and conclusions, the researcher came up with the following recommendations.

For Junkshop Owners

1. Be aware of the prices of the scraps offered by the competitors and buyers.
2. Have a schedule plan for delivery of scrap to lessen the unloading time and exposure of employees outside.
3. Should focus on scraps that are easy to dispose and generate more profit. Maintain savings on bank to sustain the business even in the amidst the Covid-19 pandemic.
4. Come up with a budget for day-to-day operation.

For Customers

1. Be aware of unsaleable scraps.
2. Segregate scraps for faster transaction.
3. Face mask, face shield, and other PPE's should not be included in the scrap inventory.
4. Have contact with trusted junkshops for updates on prices of scraps and schedule of pick-up.
5. Personally visit the concerned junkshop to have a firsthand view of its business operation.

For Local Government Unit

1. Should have a financial plan like loans for SME's specially junkshops for them to maintain the business even in the amidst of Covid-19 pandemic.
2. Should visit junkshops to assess if they are following the health protocols.
3. Should have plan to addressing those small junkshops that do not have enough capital to sustain the business.
4. Should allow junkshop operation such as picking-up scraps from subdivisions.

5. Should allow delivery of scraps to other cities and lessen restrictions since junkshops help the community to dispose recyclable materials.

For Future Researchers

For them to explore areas of junkshop operation not taken up in this research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study aimed at minimizing the possibility of harm to the intended respondents by guaranteeing the privacy of their answers and preserving their identity both during and after the study. They gave this researcher their free and informed permission up front, and they were advised that they might withdraw from the study at any time if necessary. Since procedures were followed to obtain prior informed permission, guaranteeing voluntary participation, anonymity, and confidentiality of their replies, the study did not threaten or damage people who were selected.

Acknowledgments

This section may include a statement of gratitude in general to the people who assisted in the conduct of the study, to the respondents, to the author/s of the instruments, etc.

The researcher extends his sincerest gratitude to the following persons who had directly and indirectly assisted and guided him in the achievement and fulfillment of this study. Dr. Ramom M. Garcia, Thesis Adviser, for being a competent and supportive mentor and DR. DANA B. TEBIA, Dean, Graduates Studies, for sharing her knowledge and expertise to further improve this manuscript without them this research would not be possible.

Above all, THE ALMIGHTY GOD, for the gift of wisdom, unconditional love, blessings, and guidance HE had bestowed that made the researcher a better person.

REFERENCES

- Adeniran, A. A., & Shakantu, W. (2022). The Health and Environmental Impact of Plastic Waste Disposal in South African Townships: A Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(2), 779.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19020779>
- Arenas, V. C. (2022). Junkshops as instruments for solid waste management in Iloilo City: Their characteristics, operations and economic benefits. BAHÁNDÌAN, Institutional Repository of Central Philippine University.
<https://doi.org/https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12852/285>
- Balaria, F. & Fronda, J. & Baligod, E. & Santiago, S. & Sula, C. & Pelayo, E. (2021). Junkshop Industry as Waste Recycling Business: A Green Response towards

- Economic Sustainability and Social Responsibility. *International Journal of Environment, Agriculture and Biotechnology*. 6. 025-031. 10.22161/ijeab.61.4.
- Coracero, E. & Gallego, Rb & Frago, K. & Gonzales, R. (2021). A Long-Standing Problem: A Review on the Solid Waste Management in the Philippines. *Indonesian Journal of Social and Environmental Issues (IJSEI)*. 2. 213-220. 10.47540/ijsei.v2i3.144.
- Ebner, N., & Iacovidou, E. (2021). The challenges of Covid-19 pandemic on improving plastic waste recycling rates. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 28, 726–735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.07.001>
- Elfil, M., & Negida, A. (2017). Sampling methods in Clinical Research; an Educational Review. *Emergency (Tehran, Iran)*, 5(1), e52.
- Jocson, L.M.J. 2023. Pandemic demand helped agri wages, employment recover, study concludes. *BusinessWorld*. Retrieved from: <https://www.pids.gov.ph/publication/discussion-papers/effects-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-employment-and-wages-in-the-philippines>
- McCombes, S., 2019. Descriptive Research | Definition, Types, Methods & Examples. Retrieved from: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Romallosa, A. R. D., Penetrante, M. O. T. ., & Ravena, N. G. . (2024). Junkshops as Recycling Chain Actors in the Recovery of Waste Resources from a Highly Urbanized City in the Philippines. *Applied Environmental Research*, 46(3). <https://doi.org/10.35762/AER.2024039>
- Simkus, J. (2022, November 3). Convenience Sampling: Definition, Method and Examples. Retrieved from Simply Psychology website: <https://www.simplypsychology.org/convenience-sampling.html>